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Isolation and Identification of Organic Constituent and its Antioxidant Activities of *Murdannia edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho Roots)

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Abstract— In this research work, one of the medicinal plants, Roots of *Murdannia edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) was collected from Tamu District, Sagaing Region from February to April, 2016. Firstly, it was identified at Department of Botany, University of Yangon. The phytochemical constituents were mentioned according to the reported methods. One of the bioactive compounds from active ethanol extract: syringic acid, C₉H₁₀O₅, (0.15%, R_f = 0.42, mp = 198-199 °C) was totally isolated from *Murdannia edulis* (Myit-Cho) by using solvent system toluene:diethylether (1:1) v/v saturated with 10% acetic acid on the preparative thin layer chromatography method. This isolated compound of syringic acid was identified by UV visible, FT IR and ¹HNMR spectroscopy. The characteristic bands at 2929 and 2860 cm⁻¹ showed the presence of aromatic O-CH₃ group and 1546 cm⁻¹ also expressed the presence C double bond C (C=C) stretching of aromatic ring. The ¹HNMR spectrum of this compound exhibited one proton in (OH group) at 3.5 ppm as a singlet. Two methoxy protons appeared as a singlet at 3.62 ppm which indicated that the -OCH₃ group. The signals at 7.23 (s) and 9.1 (s) ppm were due to the protons of 2-H, 6-H and one hydrogen in -COOH group. By the antioxidant activity, the IC₅₀ value, the radical scavenging activity of this syringic acid was found that more potent activity than that of standard ascorbic acid evaluated by DPPH assay method.

Keywords: *Manihot esculenta*, syringic acid, antioxidant, methoxy protons

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Murdannia edulis (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho Roots)

The herbs of *Murdannia edulis* (Stokes) Faden

Fig. 1. Photograph of *Murdannia edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho)

Fig.2. Roots and leaves of *Murdannia edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho)

(Myit-Cho) are perennial plants. The roots are fibrous, robust, to more than 10 cm thickened near end into tubers to 8 mm in diameter. The stems are several from rosette, scapiform, sub equaling leaves, ca. 2 mm in diam., sub glabrous to densely hispidulous. The leaves are all basal, leaf blade linear, glabrous or sparsely puberulent on both surfaces. The petals are pink or purple and obovate-orbicular, [1]. It is distributed in forests; near sea level to 1000 m especially in China, Hainan, Taiwan, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam [2]. The medicinal

uses of *M. edulis* (Myit-Cho) are well-known Indian ayurvedic medicinal plant [3]. The roots are used for the treatment of headache, fever, jaundice and dizziness. It is also effective for treatment of snake bite. The leaves are used for the relief of asthma, colic, pile and urinary incontinence. Powdered roots mixed with sugar are aphrodisiac and leaves are also used for the treatment of spermatorrhoea [7]. Extraction is the separation of medicinally active portions of plant tissues using selective solvents through standard procedures [4], [5]. During extraction, solvents diffuse into the solid plant material and solubilize compounds with similar polarity [6]. The purpose of standardized extraction procedures for crude medicinal plant parts is to attain the therapeutically desired portions and to eliminate unwanted material by treatment with a selective solvent [7]. The obtained products contain complex mixture of many medicinal plant metabolites, such as alkaloids, glycosides, terpenoids, flavonoids and lignin [8]. Thus, use of plant extracts and phytochemicals are of great significance in therapeutic treatments. The therapeutic effects of herbal drugs are due to chemical substances called "active principles". They can be extracted from the plant and produce effects which are similar to, but more potent and reliable than those of crude drugs [9]. Most of the active principles belong to the groups of the chemical substances such as organic acids, alkaloids, carbohydrate, gums, oils, glycosides, saponins, resins, tannins, flavonoids and enzymes etc. [11],[12]. The classification of secondary active metabolites consists of terpenoids, alkaloids, and phenolics. Glycosides, tannins, and saponins are part of the phenolics that are classified according to their specific structure [13],[14][15].

Some researchers have reported that the roots are used for the treatment of sore throat, carbuncles, eczema, asthma, emetic and expectorant. However, the antioxidant activity and isolation of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) are rarely reported in Myanmar. Therefore, in this study the phytochemical constituents, nutritional value, elemental analysis and isolation of roots of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) were studied. Moreover, antioxidant activity of isolated compounds from *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) were also conducted by different methods. Furthermore, some bioactive constituents of roots of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) were also isolated by preparative thin layer chromatographic separation method.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Sample Collection

The roots of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) samples were collected from Tamu District, Sagaing Division from February to April, 2016. Firstly, it was identified at Department of Botany, University of Yangon. The phytochemical constituents were mentioned according to the reported methods.

B. Preliminary Phytochemical Investigation of *M. edulis*

In order to find out types of phytoorganic constituents such as alkaloids, α -amino acids, carbohydrate, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, steroids, phenolic compounds, tannins and terpenoids present in the sample, preliminary phytochemical tests were carried out according to the appropriate reported methods [4].

C. Determination of some Nutritional Values of *M. edulis*

The moisture content, the ash content, the fat content, the protein content by macro Kjeldahl method and the fiber content the energy value were determined by AOAC method.

D. Quantitative Elemental Analysis by Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS)

The preparation of *M. edulis* sample solution was ready for analysis of mineral elements by AAS.

E. Isolation of ethanol extract by preparative thin layer chromatography (PTLC) method

One hundred milligrams of ethanolic extract of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden was taken and dissolved in small amount of methanol. Using capillary tube, all amount of dissolved extract was applied on PTLC plates (Kieselgel 60 F254, Merck. Co. Inc) of sizes 10 x 10 cm and the TLC plates were eluted in glass chamber containing the solvent of Toluene - Diethylether (1:1) v/v saturated with 10% acetic acid. Then, this PTLC plates was dried and placed under UV lamps. UV active spots under 356 nm corresponding to R_f of compound **1** were circled with pencil. The circled spots of compound **1** together with silica gel were scraped with specula and placed in a test tube. It was dissolved with methanol and stand for 24 hours. On the next day, it was thoroughly mixed by using vortex mixer for 30 minutes and then centrifuged on 2000 rpm for 10 minutes. The upper layer of the solvent containing compound **1** was collected into a small bottle and methanol was evaporated under the cooling fan. The net weight of the compound **1** was noted. On the next day, a small amount of the compound **1** was dissolved in methanol again and spotted on PTLC plates with extract side by side to confirm the presence of compound **1**. The compound **1** was stored in refrigerator for further testing.

F. Characterization of Isolated Compounds

1. Determination of R_f Value: The R_f value of the isolated compounds were calculated according to the following equation:

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance moved by sample}}{\text{Distance moved by solvent}}$$

II. Classification of Isolated Compounds by

Physicochemical Test: The isolated compounds were characterized by some colour test such as 5% H_2SO_4 , Libermann Burchard, anisaldehyde/ sulphuric acid, 10% $FeCl_3$ and Dragendorff's reagent. A chromatogram was prepared by developing in toluene:diethyl ether (1:1v/v) solvent system. Then the chromatogram was sprayed with 5% H_2SO_4 followed by heating, Libermann Burchard followed by heating, anisaldehyde/sulphuric acid followed by heating, 10% $FeCl_3$ and Dragendorff's reagent. The observed colouration were denoted.

III. Identification of Isolated Compound **1** from *M. edulis* : The isolated compound **1** from *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit- Cho root) was identified by modern spectroscopic techniques such as UV-Visible, FT-IR and 1H NMR spectroscopy [10].

G. Screening of Antioxidant Activity of *M. edulis*

The antioxidant activities of isolated syringic acid and standard ascorbic acid were carried out by DPPH (1,1 Diphenyl, 2-picryl-hydrazyl) radical scavenging assay using UV- visible spectrophotometer. About 2 mg of tested sample syringic acid and ascorbic acid were dissolved in 10 mL of 95 % ethanol and thoroughly mixed by vortex mixer. The mixture solution was filtered and filtrate was used as a stock solution. Desired concentrations (400, 200, 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.125 μ g/mL) of sample solutions were prepared from the stock solution by serial dilution with appropriate solvent. Then, 2.364 mg of DPPH was thoroughly dissolved in 100 mL of 95 % ethanol. This solution was freshly prepared in the brown colored flask and kept in refrigerator for no longer than 24 hours. The blank solution was prepared by mixing 1.5 mL of the test sample solution with 1.5 mL of 95 % ethanol. The control solution was prepared by mixing of 60 μ M DPPH solution and 1.5 mL of 95 % ethanol using vortex mixer. The sample solution was also prepared by mixing thoroughly 1.5 mL of DPPH solution and 1.5 mL of test sample solution. The solution were allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes, the absorbance of these solution was measured at 517 nm by UV-visible spectrophotometer. Absorbance measurements were done in triplicate for each solution and the mean values so obtained were used to calculate the percent inhibition of oxidation by the following equation (Figure 3), (Figure 4) and (Figure 5) (Figure 6). Then, IC_{50} (50 % oxidative inhibitory concentration) values were also calculated by linear regressive excel program.

Fig.3. (a) Preparation of DPPH Solution (b) control = DPPH + Ethanol, Blank=Sample + Ethanol

Fig.4. Preparation of serial dilution from *M. edulis* (Myit-Cho root) (a) syringic acid and (b) ascorbic acid

Fig.5. Preparation of extract and DPPH solution from *M. edulis* (Myit- Cho root) (a) syringic acid + DPPH (b) ascorbic acid+ DPPH

Fig.6. (a) Shaking of mixture DPPH and tested sample for one hour with orbital shaker (b) UV visible Spectrophotometer

Fig.7. TLC chromatogram of isolated compound 1 spraying with 10% FeCl₃ from ethanol extract of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sample Collection and Phytochemical Investigation of *M. edulis*

The young roots of *M. edulis* (Myit-Cho Roots) were collected from Tamu District, Sagaing Region from February to April, 2016. The phytochemical constituents were mentioned according to the reported methods. According to these experiments, alkaloids, α -amino acid, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, saponins, steroids, tannins and terpenoids were found to be present. Whereas, Cyanogenic glycoside was not detected in collected sample, *M. edulis*.

B. Determination of some Nutritional Values of *M. edulis*

In this sample, the protein content (37.14%) was observed to contain the highest amount. In addition,

carbohydrate (29.25%) and fiber (28.49%) were also found to be higher than the other nutrient, moisture (7.39%) and ash (13.54%). The fat content (3.42%) was found to be the lowest amount in *M. edulis*.

C. Quantitative Elemental Analysis by Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS)

Mineral elements present in dried powder of young shoots from *M. edulis* were determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS). Ca (108.68ppm) and Mg (125.21) were found to contain as major constituents but Fe (39.54 ppm) as trace elements and Cd, Cu, Mn, As and Pb were not detected in it.

D. Isolation of some Organic Constituents from Ethanol Extract of *M. edulis*

About one hundred milligrams of ethanolic extract of *M. edulis* was treated in small amount of methanol and applied on PTLC plates eluted in glass chamber containing the solvent of toluene - diethylether (1:1) v/v saturated with 10% acetic acid. Then, this PTLC plates was dried and placed under UV lamps R_f of compound 1 were circled with pencil, silica gel were scraped with specula and placed in a test tube. It was dissolved with methanol and stand for 24 hours. On the next day, it was thoroughly mixed by using vortex mixer for 30 minutes and then centrifuged on 2000 rpm for 10 minutes. The upper layer of the solvent containing compound 1 was collected into a small bottle and methanol was evaporated under the cooling fan. The net weight of the compound 1 was noted. On the next day, a small amount of the compound 1 was dissolved in methanol again and spotted on PTLC plates with extract side by side to confirm the presence of compound 1. The compound 1 was stored in refrigerator for further testing.

E. Classification Isolated Compounds by Colour Reaction Test

The active isolated compound 1 (toluene:diethyl ether) (1:1v/v) saturated with acetic acid were observed that pink colour testing with vanillin sulphuric acid and heating and violet colour was observed spraying with anisaldehyde sulphuric acid and heating on TLC. The isolated compound 1 could be detected as a dark yellow fluorescence on TLC under UV-365 nm light and appeared as an orange zone immediately on spraying with Dragendorff reagent. Therefore, the isolated compound 1 from may be alkaloid compound as shown in Figure 7, Table 1,2,3,4.

TABLE.I. SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF ISOLATED COMPOUNDS FROM *M. EDULIS*

Isolate d Com pounds	Phy sical state	Melti ng point (°C)	R_f	Solven t system	Solubility					
					PE	EtO Ac	Et O H	Me O H	CH Cl ₃	H ₂ O
1	Colou rless crysta l	198-199	0.42	toluene :diethy l ether (1:1 v/v)	+	+	+	+	+	+

(+) = soluble

(-) = insoluble

TABLE.II. RESULTS OF COLOUR TESTS ON TLC OF ISOLATED COMPOUNDS FROM *M. EDULIS*

No	Spraying reagents	Observation on the test of isolated compounds 1
1	5 % H ₂ SO ₄ , Δ	ND
2	Vanillin + H ₂ SO ₄ , Δ	ND
3	Anisaldehyde+H ₂ SO ₄ , Δ	ND
4	10 % FeCl ₃	orange
5	Dragendorff's	ND

ND = not detected

TABLE.III. CLASSIFICATION OF ISOLATED COMPOUNDS FROM *M. EDULIS*

No.	Reagent tested					Remarks
	Acetic anhydride and H ₂ SO ₄ in CHCl ₃	Mg and Conc: HCl in EtOH	1 % FeCl ₃ in EtOH	Dragendorff's	Bromothymol blue	
1	-	-	+	-	-	Phenolic compound may be present

(-) = not detected

F. Physicochemical properties of isolated active compound 1 *M. edulis*

The isolated active compound (1) was visualized as a dark fluorescence spot on the TLC plate under UV light of 254 and 365 nm wavelengths. The compound on the plate was localized by spraying with Dragendorff reagent and the orange color of spot which appeared on the plate can be viewed in day light. The R_f value of the spot on TLC plate was 0.42. Melting point of the isolated active compound was 198-199°C. The physicochemical data of isolated compound was identical with those of reported data in Merck index (2001).

TABLE.IV. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ISOLATED ACTIVE COMPOUND 1 FROM *M. EDULIS*

Test	Observation	Reported data*	Remark
Melting point (°C)	198-199	199-201*	From methanol
R _f	0.42		toluene:diethylether (1:1) v/v
UV (254, 365nm)	Active	Active	Conjugated double bond present
10% FeCl ₃	Dark yellow	Dark yellow	Phenolic compound may be present

* Merck Index, 2001

G. Identification of Isolated Compound 1 from Ethanol Extract of *M. edulis*

From the UV-visual spectroscopic study of isolated compound 1, it was observed that the maximum absorption wavelength (λ) were at 229 and 268 nm. The uv spectrum of isolated compound was showed in Figure 8 and Table 5. It suggests that the compound (1) consists of double bond conjugated system. From the UV-Vis spectral analysis, compound 1 may be a syringic acid. The presence of OH group and α, β-unsaturated C = O group could also be confirmed with the peak appeared at 3450 cm⁻¹ and

1637 cm⁻¹ in FT-IR spectrum of compound 1, Figure 9 and Table 6 respectively. The characteristic bands at 2929 and 2860 cm⁻¹ showed the presence of aromatic O-CH₃ group and 1546 cm⁻¹ also expressed the presence C double bond C (C=C) stretching of aromatic ring. The ¹HNMR spectrum of compound 1 exhibited one proton in (OH group) at 3.5 ppm as a singlet. Two methoxy protons appeared as a singlet at 3.62 ppm which indicated that the -OCH₃ group is Figure 10 and Table 7. The signals at 7.23 (s) and 9.1 (s) ppm were due to the protons of 2-H, 6-H and one hydrogen in -COOH group. Therefore the structure of compound 1 was assigned as follows.

The ¹HNMR spectral data of compound 1 were also found to be identical with the reported data for Syringic acid [16].

Fig.8. UV-Visible Spectra of isolated compound 1 from ethanol extract of *M. edulis*TABLE.V. UV-VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA OF ISOLATED COMPOUND 1 FROM ETHANOL EXTRACT OF *M. EDULIS*

Reagent	Observed max(nm)	Reported λmax(nm)	Remark
MeOH	229, 268	210, 263	double bond conjugation (π-π*)

Fig.9. TIR Spectra of isolated compound 1 from ethanol extract of *M. edulis*

TABLE VI. FT-IR SPECTRAL DATA OF ISOLATED COMPOUND 1 FROM *M. EDULIS*

Wave Number(cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
3450	ν_{O-H} (OH stretching of carboxylic acid group)
2929	ν_{C-H} (CH stretching of methoxy group)
2860	ν_{C-H} (CH stretching of methoxy group)
1637	$\nu_{C=O}$ (α, β -unsaturated carbonyl group)
1546	$\nu_{C=C}$ (C=C stretching of aromatic ring)
1413	δ_{C-H} (CH bending of methoxy group)
1340	δ_{O-H} (OH in plane bending)
1103	ν_{C-O} (C-OH- stretching)

TABLE VII. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUND 1 FROM ETHANOL EXTRACT OF *M. EDULIS*

Chemical Shifts (δ /ppm)		Multiplicity	Remark
Observed	Reported (Bose, 2011)		
3.5	3.8	s	1H (OH)
3.62	3.823	s	6H (hydrogen in two methoxy group)
7.23	7.23	s	2H (2-H and 6-H)
9.1	9.2	s	1H (Hydrogen in -COOH)

Fig.9. FTIR Spectra of isolated compound 1 from ethanol extract of *M. edulis*

Total H = 10
 $C_9H_{10}O_5 = 109.17 \text{ gmol}^{-1}$

Fig.10. ¹H NMR spectrum of isolated compound 1 from ethanol extract

I. Antioxidant Activity of *M. edulis* (Stokes)

Faden by DPPH Method: The antioxidant activities of two kinds of tested samples syringic acid and ascorbic acid were studied by DPPH method. This method is based on the reduction of colored of free radical DPPH in ethanolic solution by different concentrations of sample. The antioxidant activity was expressed as 50 % oxidative inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀). The lower the IC₅₀ values, the higher the antioxidant activity of the sample. In this experiment, each sample was dissolved in ethanol to get 2 mg/mL concentration and then it was diluted with ethanol to obtain 400, 200, 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration. After mixing with DPPH solution, the absorbance of each solution was measured at 517 nm. The antioxidant potential of samples can be determined by IC₅₀ (50 % inhibition concentration). The IC₅₀ values for each sample were determined by linear regressive excel program. By using DPPH free radical scavenging assay the IC₅₀ value of syringic acid was found as 4.98 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and that of standard ascorbic acid was 5.99 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Both extracts showed the anti-oxidative efficiency even though slightly higher activity in compare with standard ascorbic acid. Among them, the syringic acid of *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit- Cho Root) was found to the most potent antioxidant activity than standard ascorbic acid. The results of antioxidant activity are shown in Table 8 and Figures 11 and 12.

TABLE VIII. OXIDATIVE PERCENT INHIBITIONS AND IC₅₀ VALUES OF SYRINGIC ACID OF *M. EDULIS* (MYIT-CHO ROOT) AND

Sample	% Inhibitions (Mean $\pm$ SD) in various Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)								IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
	3.125	6.25	12.5	25	50	100	200	400	
Syringic Acid	32.27 $\pm$ 0.75	51.92 $\pm$ 0.6	58.21 $\pm$ 0.61	62.2 $\pm$ 0.61	70.2 $\pm$ 0.61	77.37 $\pm$ 0.8	78.34 $\pm$ 0.81	83.97 $\pm$ 0.14	5.96
Ascorbic acid	45.74 $\pm$ 0.71	61.58 $\pm$ 0.61	68.22 $\pm$ 0.81	70.11 $\pm$ 0.87	79.27 $\pm$ 0.22	83.4 $\pm$ 0.63	90.23 $\pm$ 0.63	98.24 $\pm$ 0.58	9.69

STANDARD ASCORBIC ACID

Fig.11. A bar graph of IC₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) values of different concentration of watery extract, 95 % EtOH extracts and standard ascorbic acid from *M. edulis* (Myit-Cho)

Fig.12. Percent inhibition of IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) values of different concentration of syringic acid from *M. edulis* (Myit- Cho Root) and standard ascorbic acid

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The overall assessments of the research work, the preliminary phytochemical investigation indicated that alkaloids, α -amino acid, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, saponins, steroids, tannins and terpenoids were present in from *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho). Among them, cyanogenic glycosides was not detected in *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho). One of the bioactive compounds from active ethanol extract 1: syringic acid (0.15%, $R_f = 0.42$, mp = 198-199 °C) was totally isolated from *M. edulis* (Stokes) Faden (Myit-Cho) by using solvent system toluene-diethylether (1:1) v/v saturated with 10% acetic acid on the preparative thin layer chromatography method. This compound was identified structurally by modern spectroscopy:UV, FTIR and ^1H NMR. In addition, the IC_{50} value of syringic acid was found as 5.96 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and that of standard ascorbic acid was 9.69 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ the by using DPPH free radical scavenging assay method. The IC_{50} value of syringic acid showed slightly greater the anti-oxidant activity than compare with standard ascorbic acid.

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